

Right-Libertarian Theory of History. Part I: A refutation of Marxist Historical Materialism

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Abstract

The theory of libertarian capitalism is founded on the general principle of private property, which implies that social relations are based not on material but on ideological factors. Thus, capitalism is not, as Marxism posits, a mode of material production determined by the productive forces of the means of production. On the contrary, capitalism is the commercial exchange that arises from social relations established according to the right of private ownership of means of production. Therefore, the economy is not the material basis that determines politics; rather, it is politics and its legal relations that determine the economy. Considering this, the theory of historical materialism is scientifically inconsistent, since the economy is an ideological superstructure based on the ideological structure of property rights, which is the foundation of politics.

Keyword: Private Property, Libertarian Capitalism, Ideology, Historical Materialism, Class Struggle, Social Class.

Introduction

The right-libertarianism, also known as anarcho-capitalism, has as its principal axiom the principle of the right to private property, which is the legal basis that determines both the political and economic relations of society. In the political domain, private property gives rise to two foundational principles of social relations: the right to absolute ownership of oneself, that is, private ownership of body, and the absolute right to private ownership of things (Rothbard, 2012: 85). It follows from the above that private property is inviolable, and therefore social relations are determined by the non-aggression axiom (Rothbard, 2012: 27). In other words, private property is the cause, and non-aggression is its effect. Consequently, Samuel E. Konkin III was wrong to assert that libertarian theory has as its general principle non-aggression axiom: “Libertarianism elaborates an entire philosophy from one simple premise: initiatory violence or its threat (coercion) is wrong (immoral, evil, bad, supremely impractical, etc.) and is forbidden; nothing else is” (Konkin, 2006: 17). The true premise is the private property right, not the non-aggression axiom. If the absolute private property right over the body is lost, the non-aggression axiom immediately loses its validity.

On the other hand, in the economics domain, private ownership on things determines how individuals exchange goods commercially in the market; that is, private property is the foundation of price fluctuations according to the law of supply and demand. Therefore, without private property, a capitalist economy cannot exist.

Politics determines economics

This last point allows infer an important consequence, not only for the theory of right-libertarianism, but for all social sciences: that politics, which is a legal structure that organizes society, determines the economic structure, so there is a causal relationship between politics and economics. However, the consequences of this assertion do not end there, since, from a theoretical point of view, it completely refutes the historical materialism of Marx. First, it demonstrates that the economy is not a material, physical structure, but rather an ideological one, since it does not arise from the productive forces of the means of production, but from property relations. Thus, Capitalism is not a mode of production or a particular level of technological development of machines. Although it may seem hard to believe, Marx did not define capitalism according to the private ownership of the means of production but rather refers exclusively to the economy that employs automated machines and many individuals in industries.

In Marx's words, capitalism is the following: "Capitalist production only then really begins, as we have already seen, when each individual capital employs simultaneously a comparatively large number of labourers; when consequently the labour process is carried on an extensive scale and yields, relatively, large quantities of products" (Marx, 1996: 326-327). To make the above more understandable, it is necessary to connect that definition of capitalism with the following statement by Marx, that perfectly summarizes it: "The hand-mill gives you society with the feudal lord; the steam-mill, society with the industrial capitalist." (Marx, 1976: 166). Thus, for Marx, capitalism is not the economy founded on private property; it is only a specific stage in the technological evolution of production.

On the contrary, capitalism is the way in which the exchange of goods occurs according to the right of private property. Private property is what allows for speculation and price setting, that is, economic freedom. Ludwig von Mises was clear in stating that private ownership is what creates the capitalist or free market economy: "Private ownership of the means of production is the fundamental institution of the market economy" (Mises, 1998: 678). Furthermore, this serious error of Marx was already exposed by Rothbard: "In addition to these logical flaws, the materialist doctrine is factually absurd. Obviously, the hand mill, which ruled in ancient Sumer, did not 'give you' a feudal society there: furthermore, there were capitalist relations long before the steam mill" (Rothbard, 2006: 374).

The other thing that demonstrates the ideological nature of economics is that Marxism is wrong to claim that economics is the basis that determines politics. Historical materialism posits that the productive forces, which are the means of production or machines, create specific relations of

production among individuals according to their level of technological development. This is the same as saying that the division of labor is formed according to the means of production. Thus, the machines and tools used in production, along with the type of division of labor, constitute the material base or economic structure that conditions the ideological formation of society as its superstructure. Therefore, every change in the means of production determines a specific form of politics and culture in general. Historical materialism, in Marx's words, is as follows:

“The totality of these relations of production constitutes the economic structure of society, the real foundation, on which arises a legal and political superstructure and to which correspond definite forms of social consciousness. The mode of production of material life conditions the general process of social, political and intellectual life” (Marx, 1987: 263).

The principle established by Marx posits that all ideas accepted as valid by individuals are a product of the technological conditions of production. If a new means of production replaces the previous means of production, this change in the relations of production leads to a change in the dominant ideas of society. Marx expressed this as follows:

“No social formation is ever destroyed before all the productive forces for which it is sufficient have been developed, and new superior relations of productions never replace older ones before the material conditions for their existence have matured within the framework of the old society” (Marx, 1987: 263).

Despite the supposedly indisputable logic with which Marx presents his theory of historical materialism, it has serious inconsistencies. First, technological change in the productive forces only directly affects the types of functions that comprise the division of labor within production, as certain jobs disappear because they become unnecessary, while new jobs are created. This is where Schumpeter's principle of creative destruction of capitalism applies (Schumpeter, 1942: 83). However, politics, laws, and culture in general remain unaffected, as the system of private property, tariffs, and state monopolies, if they exist, remain unchanged. A mode of production produces in the same way in both capitalism and communism; the only difference between the two economic systems is the type of distribution that the market establishes according to the type of ownership: private or collective. Therefore, the economy is not a material structure, but, like politics and legal, it is an ideological structure.

The economy as an ideological structure

If a society is politically organized according to the right to private ownership, its economy will be capitalist. Similarly, if a society is constituted according to the right to collective ownership, its economy will be socialist. A change in the right to property results in a change in the economy. Althusser is wrong to deny that the socialist economy is not a consequence of collective property:

“For to talk about collective ownership of the means of production is to talk about, not socialist relations of productions, but, let us say, socialist law, and to mistake (so-called) socialist law for socialist relations of production. If we stick to this purely legal definition of the socialist mode of production, we risk very serious disillusion. Experience is there to prove it” (Althusser, 2014: 60-61).

And it is not necessary to resort the theorist from the Austrian School of Economics to refute this. Simply quoting Marx is enough to demonstrate that economics is an ideological system that arises from politics itself. To do this, one must analyze the Marxist theory of communist revolution, which states that communism can only be established through the collectivization of the means of production. In other words, a communist economy can only be established after the replacement of the right to private property with that of collective property. This, in Marx and Engel’s words: “In this sense, the theory of the Communists may be summed up in the single sentence: Abolition of private property” (Marx and Engels, 1976: 498). No matter what type of productive force and relations of production exist in society. Communism can never be imposed economically without the prior political approval of the abolition of private property and its replacement by collective ownership of the means of production under state control.

Furthermore, another important evidence that demonstrates economics is an ideological structure originating in politics is the fact that Marx argued that class struggle is not an economic struggle, but a political struggle aimed at conquering the political power of the State: “But the struggle of class against class is a political struggle” (Marx, 1976: 211). If the economic structure is supposed to determine the ideology of society, then why must the class struggle begin in the political domain to subsequently transform the economics domain? Are not the theory of class struggles irrefutable evidence that Marxism’s materialist interpretation of history is entirely unscientific? It is undeniable that this is the case. Another important detail is that class struggles require the creation of conflict through ideological propaganda. This means that the class consciousness of the proletariat is nothing other than the implantation of communist consciousness in the minds of individuals who desire to carry out the communist revolution.

For this to be effective, the creation of communist political consciousness must be directed by a political party that leads the communist revolution, otherwise the proletarian class will continue to think about its own social existence in capitalist terms. This is why Marx and Engels maintained that the dissemination of the idea of communist consciousness among the workers could only be achieved through the leadership of a communist political party: “The immediate aim of the Communists is the same as that of all other proletarian parties: formation of the proletarian into a class, overthrow of the bourgeois supremacy, conquest of political power by the proletariat” (Marx and Engels, 1976: 498). In short, a communist revolution will never happen without a communist political party organizing it. In other words, Marx and Engels’ approach is nothing more than social engineering. Revolution is never spontaneous but artificially created.

This was explained more explicitly by Lenin: “Without such organisation the proletariat will never rise to the class-conscious struggle; without such organisation the working-class movement is doomed to impotency” (Lenin, 1964: 370). In the case of a right-libertarian revolution, the existence of a political party is essential for the right-wing libertarian movement to achieve its goals. Without an organization to lead the movement, right-libertarian ideas will only exist in theory, not in practice. And the right-libertarian revolution need not necessarily be violent. While it is true that Rothbard argued that the destruction of a state can only occur violently, whether through a war of conquest by another state or through a revolutionary war (Rothbard, 2009: 44), that is, a civil war, these assertions are nothing more than a reductionist view. There is the alternative of carrying out a right-libertarian revolution peacefully, but this requires certain conditions, which will not be addressed here but rather in subsequent investigation.

The class struggle as ideological struggle

The class struggle is not a struggle between the business class and the working class; on the contrary, the class struggle is essentially a struggle between the class that defends communist ideas and the class that defends capitalist ideas. This means that the ideologically communist class is made up of business owners, and that the ideologically capitalist class can be made up of workers. In the economic domain, the business and working classes depend on each other. The business owner needs wage labor, and the wage earner needs the business owner to hire their services. The only way that class struggle can break out is if there are two classes defending two opposing systems of property rights; that is, if there are an ideological communist class and an ideologically capitalist class. As Ludwig von Mises rightly argued, the social organization of individuals is a consequence of ideology. It is ideology that determines human action: “Society is a product of human action. Human action is directed by ideologies. Thus society and any concrete order of social affairs are an outcome of ideologies (...)” (Mises, 1998: 188).

An important fact that demonstrates the validity of Mises’ thesis is that Marxist social classes, although they are the result of economic relations, the formation of each of them is of a legal nature, since a social class is made up of individuals who possess the same type of property as their main means of livelihood. Therefore, the Marxist theory of the formation of social classes is ideological in nature. To demonstrate this fact, it is necessary to quote what Marx defined as social class:

“The owners merely of labour power, owners of capital, and landowners, whose respective sources of income are wages, profit and ground rent, in other words, wage labourers, capitalists and landowners, constitute then three big classes of modern society based upon the capitalist mode of production” (Marx, 1998: 870).

While Marx’s categorization of social classes is well structured, the underlying reason for this organization is flawed. The working class, the capitalist class and the landowning class are not a consequence of capitalist mode production, but rather of the right to private property. The working

class is the owning class that lives off its labor power; the capitalist class is the owning class that lives off the profits from its means of production; and finally, the landowning class is the owning class that lives off the rent from land leased to others. Hence, social classes are logical constructs established ideologically according to the type of property individuals possess. This does not imply the spontaneous existence of a class identity but rather serves as a means of socioeconomic classification. Rothbard demonstrated this fact in the following way:

“A ‘class’ is a set of entities with one identifiable thing in common. (...) A ‘social class’ is a class of human beings with one thing in common. (...) But from our point of view, in a study of the Marxian theory of class, these classes are all worthless because there is no inherent conflict between them” (Rothbard, 2006: 380)

However, an individual’s membership in one class does not preclude them from belonging to the other two. A wage earner can also be capitalist or a rentier, or a rentier can be a capitalist or a wage earner. To define social classes as irreconcilable with one another is a reductionism artificially created by Marxism to justify its revolutionary theory.

Conclusion

Thus, it is irrefutably demonstrated that Marxism is completely wrong in its supposedly scientific assumptions. For Marx, Engels, Lenin, and Marxists in general, historical materialism is the only theory that elevates sociology and history to the level of science. This overconfidence and naiveté of Marxism is perfectly summarized in the following words of Lenin: “Materialism is not ‘primarily a scientific conception of history,’ as Mr. Mihailovsky thinks, but the only scientific conception of it” (Lenin, 1986: 142). However, the opposite has been demonstrated that a scientific theory of society is a theory founded on the causality of ideas. In other words, the true scientific theory of society is a science of ideology, and its general principle is the law of human action, which Ludwig von Mises called praxeology.

The theory of human action in the social domain demonstrates that not only is the economy an ideological system, but it is also an ideological consequence of the political system. If the type of property rights in a society is not politically defined, the society itself disintegrates because there is no common legal framework defining the mutual recognition of individual property rights. In that sense, Locke was clear in stating that if individuals accept to live in society it is because each one wants to ensure the recognition of the ownership rights: “(...) and is willing to join in society with others, who are already united, or have a mind to unite, for the mutual preservation of their lives, liberties and estates, which I call by the general name, property” (Locke, 1980: 66). Thus, without mutual recognition of individual property, not only does society disintegrate, but cooperation between individuals through the division of labor also becomes impossible.

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